

Trivalent Cobalt as an Oxidising Reagent for Volumetric Estimations. Determination of Oxalic, Mandelic and Phenyl Acetic Acids.

D. D. Mishra and J. K. Sthapak

Cobalt (III) in acid medium can quantitatively oxidise a large number of organic compounds, viz., ethylene glycol, malic, tartaric and citric acids¹. However, it cannot be directly heated with any one of these compounds due to the possibility of its reduction with water. Therefore, an excess of Mn (II) Sulphate over that of Cobalt (III), as an intermediate along with the organic compounds was taken. The experimental procedure was similar to that as has been described earlier².

Cobalt (III) complex oxidises Mn (II) to its higher valency states amongst which the percentage of Mn (IV) is generally higher. This oxidant is stable even if it is heated for a longer time. Oxalic acid is oxidised even in cold, but for other compounds, heating to boiling is necessary and the oxidation proceeds to the formation of benzaldehyde. The unreacted oxidant is estimated iodometrically.

The results have been found to be reproducible and are given below :

TABLE I

No.	Amount taken (in mg.)	Amount found (in mg.)	Percentage max. deviation
1.	15.75	15.79	0.25
2.	38.00	37.93	0.20
3.	34.00	33.88	0.35

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Department of Applied Chemistry,
Government Engineering College,
Jabalpur, M.P.

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